

ENA Data Retrieval Practical

As we have discussed, data at the ENA can be retrieved using:

- ENA Advanced Search
- ENA Portal API
- ENA Reports API (metadata only)
- ENA Browser API

All public data at the ENA is openly available to search and download from the FTP. During this workshop, you will be retrieving public data and then downloading some of the data onto your computer.

You will be making use of the Advanced Search, Portal API, Browser API and the Reports API for this workshop.

Some of these exercises require use of the command-line. Where there is a command to run, it will be provided for you mostly complete, indicated by an indented line beginning with a dollar ('\$') sign. Do not enter the \$, just the text following it. Some commands have been left incomplete for you to fill in, so read them carefully before you enter them.

Exercise 1: Advanced Search

You will be using the ENA advanced search to build queries to be able to answer the questions in this exercise.

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>

Remember that in order to correctly build an advanced search query, you first need to focus on the data type that you are looking for. Is the data type you are trying to retrieve “Samples”, “Studies” or “Runs” etc.? You can then proceed to build your query by carefully selecting the attributes that the question is asking for.

The image displays three sequential screenshots of the ENA advanced search interface, illustrating the process of building a query. Red arrows indicate the flow from one step to the next.

- Step 1:** The "Data Type" section is active. The user selects "Nucleotide sequences" from the "Data type" dropdown menu.
- Step 2:** The "Query" section is active. The user enters the query "tax_eq(9606)". The interface shows a "Build Query" button and a "Reset" button. Below the query input, there is a section for "Type to filter query params" with a list of filter categories: "Taxonomy and related", "Geographical location", "Geography", and "Collection information". A rule is added: "NCBI Taxonomy" is set to "Homo sapiens" with an equals sign operator. There is also an option for "Include subordinate taxa".
- Step 3:** The "Query" section is active. The user enters the query "tax_eq(9606) AND description='kinase'". The interface shows a "Build Query" button and a "Reset" button. Below the query input, there is a section for "Type to filter query params" with a list of filter categories: "Taxonomy and related", "Geographical location", and "Geography". A rule is added: "Description" is set to "kinase" with an equals sign operator. There is also an option for "brief sequence description".

Please create advanced search queries to answer the following questions:

1. How many insect metagenome samples have been submitted to the INSDC?
2. How much read data has been submitted for Neanderthals (try to display only the generated fastq files in your results)?
3. How many studies have been made public since 15th February 2023?
4. How much paired read data has been made public for Homo sapiens obtained via CHIP-Seq sequencing?

Exercise 2: Portal API

Now that you have built queries on the advanced search, you have an idea of what the query looks like and the use of “AND” and “OR” parameters. You will now build a query for the portal API and use the curl command to retrieve the results in a TSV file format as output.

The query can be built from any number of fields, with logical operators and parentheses used to order the execution of each. Any text or controlled vocabulary values used within the query must be bound by double quotes.

Let's have a look at the examples below:

```
https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search?result=read_run&query=collection_date>=2016-01-01%20AND%20collection_date<=2024-12-31%20AND%20tax_eq(3755)%20AND%20country=Spain&fields=run_accession,fastq_ftp,fastq_md5,country,tax_id&limit=0
```

In the example above, I am trying to retrieve all raw read data results obtained from sequencing almond (prunus dulcis (taxID: 3755)) samples, collected from Spain, submitted to the ENA between 2016-01-01 and 2024-12-31. Try copy pasting the above url in your browser to see the results.

Let's try to run this on the command line. Open a command line terminal window on your computer.

You can use the above query to retrieve a tsv report using a curl command on the command line like below. Copy the curl command below and paste it onto your command line terminal.

```
$ curl -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" -d 'result=read_run&query=tax_eq(3755)%20AND%20country%3D%22Spain%22%20AND%20collection_date%3E%3D2016-01-01%20AND%20collection_date%3C%3D2024-12-31&fields=run_accession%2Cfastq_ftp%2Cfastq_md5%2Ccountry%2Ctax_id&format=tsv' "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search"
```

1. What run accessions (ERR123) does the above search return?

Let's list the experiments that the runs from our previous query are linked to. Enter the run accessions from the answers above in the fields labelled "TO_DO":

```
$ curl -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" -d  
'result=read_experiment&query=run_accession%3D%22TO_DO%22%20OR%20run_ac  
cession%3D%22TO_DO%22&fields=experiment_accession%2Cexperiment_title%2Crun  
_accession&format=tsv' "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search"
```

2. What experiment accessions (ERX123) does the command above return?

You can also download the results from the above query into an output file by using an "-o" flag:

```
$ curl -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" -d  
'result=read_experiment&query=run_accession%3D%22TO_DO%22%20OR%20run_ac  
cession%3D%22TO_DO%22&fields=experiment_accession%2Cexperiment_title%2Crun  
_accession&format=tsv' "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search" -o outputfile.tsv
```

Exercise 3: ENA Browser API

Types of records you can retrieve using the Browser API:

File Format	Available Record Types
XML	Study, Sample, Run, Experiment, Analysis, Taxon
EMBL Flat File (text)	Sequences (including coding and non-coding sequences), WGS sets, TSA sets
Fasta	Sequences

Now that you have some experiment accessions from the last portal API query, let's download the experiment files. You can do this programmatically with a curl command, but for this exercise, let's make use of the user interface:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/api/swagger-ui/index.html>

POST	<code>/xml</code>	Obtain records in XML format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request
POST	<code>/fasta</code>	Obtain records in FASTA file format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request
POST	<code>/embl</code>	Obtain records in EMBL flatfile format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request
GET	<code>/xml/{accession}</code>	xml
GET	<code>/versions/{accession}</code>	versions
GET	<code>/summary/{accession}</code>	summary
GET	<code>/fasta/{accession}</code>	fasta
GET	<code>/embl/{accession}</code>	Obtain records in EMBL flatfile format
GET	<code>/text/{accession}</code>	Obtain records in EMBL flatfile format

1. Access the link above for the Portal API
2. Click on `/xml/accession` to expand it as experiment data is in the form of XML files.
3. Click on "try it out" on the right and enter the experiment accessions (ERXxxx) separated by a comma.
4. Select "true" for download
5. Execute the command
6. Click on download to download the generated XML file.

7. The downloaded experiment XML will contain all the experiments with their metadata.

Exercise 4: ENA Reports API

You will now retrieve sample metadata (that is still private) submitted from your webin account using the reports API:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/report/swagger-ui/index.html>

For the purpose of this exercise, please use your Webin account and password:

Username: **Webin-xxxx**

Password: **xxxx**

The metadata you want to retrieve is from a still private sample you registered with your own Webin account.

1. Access the link to the user interface for the reports API:
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/report/swagger-ui/index.html>
2. Click on Authorise at the top right of the page and enter your Webin credentials.
3. Navigate to “samples/xml/{ids}”

4. Click on “Try it out” and enter your sample accession: **ERSxxxx**
5. Click on execute and the prompt should return an XML file with the respective sample metadata. You can download this XML to use for any further analyses.